

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Poland.....	3
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Poland: An Introduction	12
2.2. <i>The Provision of Local Public Transport</i>	15
2.3. <i>Provision of Internet Infrastructure by Local Government: A Step Towards Smart Villages</i>	18
2.4. <i>Lack of Effective Housing Management in Communes and Attempts to Recover from the Crisis</i> ...	25
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Poland: An Introduction	32
3.2. <i>Investment Expenditure of Local Governments: The Role of European Funds in the Financial Strategies of Rural gminas</i>	42
3.3. <i>Integrated Territorial Investment (ITI)</i>	46
3.4. <i>The Importance of the ‘Village Fund’ for the Mobilization of Rural Residents to Civic Participation</i>	50
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Poland: An Introduction	56
4.2. <i>What does Metropolitan Cooperation in the Functional Area of the Capital Warsaw Involve?</i>	62
4.3. <i>First Territorial Unit of Metropolitan Nature in Poland: The Metropolitan Union ‘Upper Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis’</i>	67
4.4. <i>The Association ‘Gdansk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area’ as an Example of Urban–Rural Cooperation</i>	75
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction.....	83
5.2. <i>Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government</i>	85
5.3. <i>County-Commune Unions as a New Form of Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Beskidian County and Commune Union</i>	88
5.4. <i>The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations</i>	94
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Poland: An Introduction	102
6.2. <i>Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expense of the Rural Area: Consultations with Residents or a Local Referendum?</i>	106
6.3. <i>Youth Commune Council in Poland</i>	115
6.4. <i>Participatory Fund in Cities</i>	120

Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Poland: An Introduction

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Legal Basis

The issue of financing the activities of local government in Poland was addressed in Article 167 of the Polish Constitution: 'Units of local government shall be assured public funds adequate for the performance of the duties assigned to them. Alterations to the scope of duties and authorities of units of local government shall be made in conjunction with appropriate alterations to their share of public revenues. The revenues of units of local government shall consist of their own revenues as well as general subvention and specific (targeted) grants from the State Budget of Poland. The sources of revenues for units of local government shall be specified by act.'

Since the reactivation of local government in 1990, the fourth act in this respect has been in force. Currently, it is the Act of 13 November 2003 on the Revenues of Local Government Units. It introduces a separate system of financing of *gminy* [communes, municipalities] (including cities with *powiat* rights), *powiaty* [counties], voivodships and regulates the mechanism for the elimination of income disparities between local government units.

General Structure of Public Finances

In Poland, the ratio of revenues and expenditures of local governments (*gmina*, *powiat* and voivodeship self-governments) to GDP is fairly high. In 2018, the revenue of all local government units calculated according to the methodology adopted by the European Union amounted to PLN 251.8 billion, which corresponded to 11.9 per cent of GDP (in 2008 – 13.9 per cent, in 2015 – 12.7 per cent, in 2016 – 11.5 per cent, in 2017 – 11.6 per cent)⁶⁰. This clear downward trend in the years 2008-2017 was primarily attributable to the effects of the global economic crisis. The Polish local government sub-sector is also characterized by an

⁶⁰ All statistical data prepared by the author on the basis of official documents of state authorities: Annual 'State Budget Execution Analysis' prepared by the Supreme Audit Office, <<https://www.nik.gov.pl/kontrola/analiza-budzetu-panstwa>>; Annual reports of the Statistics Poland (the Central Statistical Office), 'Financial Economy of Local Government Units', <<https://stat.gov.pl/en/topics/national-accounts/general-government-statistics/financial-economy-of-local-government-units-2018,2,15.html>>; Annual reports of the Ministry of Finance, <<https://www.gov.pl/web/finanse/sprawozdania-roczne>> and Annual reports of Regional Accounting Chambers, <https://www.rio.gov.pl/modules.php?op=modload&name=HTML&file=index&page=publ_sprawozdania> accessed 1 December 2019.

expenditure-to-GDP ratio higher than the EU average. Again, there is a downward trend in the value of the ratio (from 14.1 per cent in 2009 to 12.7 per cent in 2015).⁶¹

In comparison to other EU countries, in Poland the ratio of local government units' revenues to GDP is higher than the EU average. Out of the 21 EU unitary states with a significant range of local government activities⁶², Poland ranks sixth in terms of local government's revenues in relation to GDP. However, this does not mean that public finances in Poland have been decentralized. Despite relatively high income of the local government, it is still mostly derived from the transfer of funds from the Polish state budget.⁶³

The financial situation of local government units varies depending on the type of local government (*gmina*, *powiat* or voivodship). Cities with *powiat* rights take a special position. In addition, we observe spatial diversity in the prosperity of *gminas* attributed to local conditions (e.g. the location of industrial plants which pay part of CIT to *gminas*' budgets). The financial situation of the local government in Poland is also significantly influenced by access to financial resources from the European Union. At present, the financial condition of local governments is strongly affected by the state policy in terms of determining tasks and public finances. Moreover, changes in the financial situation of local governments in metropolitan areas (regions) may be observed.

Revenue Structure of Local Government

Figure 2: Structure of local government revenue (*gmina*, *powiat* and voivodship) in 2006 and 2018.

⁶¹ Poniatowicz Marzanna, 'Stabilność finansowa jednostek samorządu terytorialnego w aspekcie nowej perspektywy finansowej Unii Europejskiej i zmian w systemie dochodów samorządowych' (2016) 125 *Ekonomiczne Problemy Usług* 7 <<https://wnus.edu.pl/epu/file/article/view/2740.pdf>> accessed 1 December 2019.

⁶² Excluding Cyprus, Malta and Luxembourg, where the scope of local government activity is fairly limited.

⁶³ College of the Supreme Audit Office, 'Analysis of State Budget Execution and Monetary Policy Objectives in 2015' (Supreme Audit Office 2016) 260 <<https://www.nik.gov.pl/plik/id,11415,vp,13764.pdf>> accessed 1 December 2019.

The largest category in the structure of revenue of local governments in Poland is own revenues which in 2018 constituted 49.3 per cent of total revenues. The remaining funds are transferred from the state budget: the share of general subvention in the revenue of the local government amounted to 22.4 per cent, while targeted grants – 28.3 per cent.⁶⁴

In the structure of own revenue of local government units, in 2018, the largest share was represented by income from the share in personal income tax (PIT) revenues – 41.0 per cent, property tax – 18.2 per cent, from the share in corporate income tax (CIT) revenues – 7.8 per cent.

Local government units in Poland are, next to enterprises, the most important category of beneficiaries of funds from the European Union. In 2007-2013, approximately 25 per cent of all funds from the EU budget allocated to Poland were used by local governments.⁶⁵ In 2018, EU funds constituted 6.7 per cent of total revenue of local government (they are classified as subsidies). In relation to the total revenue of particular types of local government units, income from the EU constituted: in *gminas* – 5.1 per cent, in cities with *powiat* rights – 5.0 per cent, in *powiats* – 6.4 per cent, in voivodships – 26.9 per cent. It should be emphasized that the absorption capacity of local government remains in close correlation with the financial standing and state of local finances.

⁶⁴ Mirosław Błażej and others, 'Financial Economy of Local Government Units 2018' (Statistics Poland 2019) 33 <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/rachunki-narodowe/statystyka-sektora-instytucji-rzadowych-i-samorzadowych/gospodarka-finansowa-jednostek-samorzadu-terytorialnego-2018,5,15.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

⁶⁵ Patrycja Chrzanowska, 'Wykorzystanie funduszy europejskich przez samorzady terytorialne w kontekście rozwoju ekonomiczno-gospodarczego gminy [Use of European Funds by Local Authorities in Economic Development Context]' (2015) 106 Zeszyty Naukowe Uniwersytetu Przyrodniczo-Humanistycznego w Siedlcach 23 <https://repozytorium.uph.edu.pl/bitstream/handle/11331/535/Chrzanowska.P_Wykorzystanie_funduszy_europejskich_przez_samorzady_terytorialne.pdf?sequence=1> accessed 15 October 2020.

Figure 3: Distribution of local government revenue among *gminas*, cities with *powiat* rights, *powiats* and voivodeships.

In the structure of revenue of all three tiers of local government (*gminas*, *powiats* and voivodeships), the highest income is allocated to the first tier of local government, i.e. *gminas* and cities with *powiat* rights – 82.2 per cent in total⁶⁶.

Gminas and cities with *powiat* rights are and will continue to be the key to achieving such objectives as equalizing the standard of living in different regions of Poland and creating conditions for local development. For this reason, the next part of the study will examine the basic level of local government in Poland, i.e. the financial situation of *gminas* (including cities with *powiat* rights).

Structure of *Gminas'* Revenue

The changes in the state of the *gmina's* finances indicate that the revenue of *gminas* is increasing annually, in 2018 it reached the level of PLN 121.4 billion. Compared to 2002, when the total revenue of *gminas* amounted to PLN 37.3 billion, this means an increase of 225 per cent over 16 years.

Figure 4: Revenue of *gminas* 2002-2018.

The 2018 revenue structure of all *gminas* and cities with *powiat* rights was as follows: own revenues 43.2 per cent, general subvention 23.4 per cent, targeted grants for commissioned tasks – 33.4 per cent.

⁶⁶ Ministry of Finance, 'Report on the Execution of the State Budget for the Period from 1 January to 31 December 2018. Information on the Execution of Budgets of Local Government Units' (Council of Ministers 2019) 11 <<https://www.gov.pl/web/finanse/zestawienia-zbiorcze>> accessed 2 November 2019.

If we divide *gminas* into rural *gminas*, urban and rural *gminas*, urban *gminas* and separately cities with *powiat* rights, the following picture emerges.

Figure 5: Structure of revenue of *gminas* (rural, urban-rural and urban) in 2007 and 2016.

Figure 6: Structure of revenue of cities with *powiat* rights in 2007 and 2016.

The general trend concerning the sources of financing of *gminas* suggests an increase in financial transfers from the state budget. In particular, the amount of targeted grants related to the social policy of the state has increased (e.g. the government program ‘Family 500 plus’, introduced on 1 April 2016, which involves financial benefits for families with children). In 2018, the grant for the ‘Family 500 plus’ program accounted for 13.8 per cent of the *gminas*’ revenue (targeted grants in total constituted 24 per cent of the *gminas*’ revenue).

The second noticeable tendency is greater dependence of rural *gminas* on financial transfers from the state budget. It pertains to general subvention intended to support *gminas* with low own revenue. Its purpose is to eliminate disproportions in the distribution of own revenue of the local government.

Categories of *Gminas*’ own Revenue

Gminas’ own revenue includes: local taxes (mainly: agricultural tax, forestry tax, tax on real estate, tax on means of transport). *Gminas* enjoy financial autonomy in this respect – they can set tax rates on their territory (within the limits set by law). Additionally, a part of the income from PIT⁶⁷ and CIT⁶⁸ is transferred to the *gmina*’s budget. PIT and tax on real estate are of fundamental importance in financing the *gmina*’s budget. The basis for taxation of real estate in Poland is its area and not its value. This has been a matter of dispute – the proposal to introduce a real estate cadaster and a cadastral tax has long been under discussion.

⁶⁷ Revenue from PIT contributes towards the budgets of *gminas* (39.34%), *powiat* budgets (10.25%), voivodship budgets (1.60%) and the state budget (49.81%).

⁶⁸ Revenue from CIT contributes towards the budgets of *gminas* (6.71%), *powiat* budgets (1.4%), voivodship budgets (14.75%) and state budget (77.14%).

Figure 7: Structure of own revenue of *gminas*.

The main problem in the area of *gmina's* revenue from PIT is the introduction of a number of tax reliefs in recent years which cause a decrease in the *gmina's* income from this source. These are decisions taken by the government and the parliament – without the participation of *gminas*. This causes great dissatisfaction and protests of local governments.

General Subvention for *Gminas*

A general subvention is a form of non-refundable financing of the local government budgets by the state budget. These are funds transferred to equalize the level of own revenue of local governments. The subvention is an instrument for eliminating income disparities between local governments. The funds from the subvention may be disbursed by the local authorities at their own discretion.

The general subvention for *gminas* consists of three parts: education, compensatory and offsetting part. In 2019, the educational part (for running schools) accounted for 77.2 per cent of the total subvention. One of the factors used for the determination of the compensatory part (apart from the amount of tax revenue per capita) is the population density in a *gmina* which is lower than the Polish average. It is an aid for rural *gminas* – sparsely populated.

The funds which are transferred to poorer *gminas* in the form of a general subvention are derived from the state budget but also from payments made by wealthy *gminas* with high income from local taxes. Such a system of redistribution of *gminas'* revenue has been objected

by wealthy *gminas* for a long time. In 2011, a citizen bill ('citizens' legislative initiative')⁶⁹ was prepared the aim of which was to reduce the amount of payments made by wealthy *gminas* to the general subvention. The bill was not seconded in parliament. In 2018, 88 *gminas* made payments to the state budget for the benefit of poorer ones (in Poland there are 2477 *gminas* in total). This means that 3.5 per cent of *gminas* in Poland participate in the system of co-financing poorer *gminas*.⁷⁰

The subvention is certainly a more predictable source of finance than other types of own revenue which are tax-related and thus largely determined by the dynamics of economic growth. During the economic slowdown, the general subvention is therefore intended to stabilize the income situation of the local government. However, its critics claim that the general subvention decreases the motivation of the *gmina's* self-government to rationalize expenditures.

Targeted Grants for *Gminas*

Targeted grants are granted *gminas* from the state budget for the execution of additional tasks (unused grants must be returned to the budget). Local government units do not have any actual influence on the grant amount. For several years, local governments have been suggesting that targeted grants are insufficient to fulfil the commissioned tasks. As a result, in order to ensure the performance of these tasks, local governments finance them from their own resources.

In recent years, the local governments of large cities have decided to file claims in civil courts against the Polish State Treasury for payment of the missing funds for the performance of commissioned tasks (the funds are primarily needed for the tasks related to keeping population registers, issuing identity cards, adjudicating in registration cases and keeping vital records). These are long and costly proceedings, however, more and more large cities are deciding to go to court. The precursor of such an action was Cracow⁷¹ which after 5 years obtained a court judgement ordering the Polish State Treasury to return the funds that Cracow allocated for co-financing of commissioned tasks.⁷² The increasing number of court cases may possibly result in a change in the methods of determining the costs of tasks commissioned by the Polish Government and Parliament.

⁶⁹ The right to submit a bill is granted in Poland to a group of at least 100 000 citizens having the right to vote in elections to the Sejm (Art 118(2) of the Polish Constitution 1997).

⁷⁰ A similar mechanism of revenues redistribution applies at the level of *powiats* and voivodeships.

⁷¹ Cracow (Kraków) - the second largest city in Poland.

⁷² Weber Maria, 'Miasta w sądzie walczą o pieniądze z rządem [Cities fight in court with the government for money]' (*Rzeczpospolita*, 22 October 2019) <<https://regiony.rp.pl/prawo/22244-zadania-trafiaja-do-sadu> > accessed 1 December 2019.

Expenses of *Gminas*

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in local government expenditure, both in the group of current and capital expenditure.⁷³ On the one hand, it results from an increase in the scope of tasks and the realization of local government investments, however, on the other hand, it is an effect of a significant increase in the costs of performing public tasks.

The most important items of the *gminas'* expenditure include 'education and upbringing' and 'family' – in total they constitute over half of the *gminas'* budget expenditure (51.4 per cent). The budget of *gminas* also disburses funds for agriculture and hunting – 2.7 per cent. Compared to 2017, expenditure on agriculture and hunting increased by 48.8 per cent. It resulted from, inter alia, the implementation of the sub-measure 'Support for investments in agricultural holdings' under the Rural Development Program for 2014-2020 financed from the EU.

Figure 8: *Gminas'* expenditure.

⁷³ In the structure of *gminas'* expenditures in 2018, current expenditures constituted 79.4% whereas capital expenditures 20.6%. If we consider rural *gminas* separately, current expenditure amounts to 78.3% and capital expenditure to 21.7%.

Salaries for employees, including teachers (approx. 34 per cent of *gmina's* expenditure) constitute a relatively considerable part of expenditures. Considering that between 2015 and 2018 salaries in the local government increased by 15.8 per cent, this places a heavy burden on the local government budget. This is a particularly difficult problem for small rural *gminas* which experience financial difficulties and propose that the financing of teachers' salaries should be assumed by the Polish state.

Capital Expenditures of *Gminas*

The main determinant of the state of local government finances, related to its role in the development policy, is the investments made. The increase in PIT revenues contributed to the achievement of an operating surplus⁷⁴ in 2018 in the local government budgets which was entirely allocated to development – i.e. investments. It was also possible thanks to subsidies of 21.5 billion from the European Union and incurring new liabilities (mainly loans) for a total amount of approx. PLN 16.2 billion. Even more investments were planned for 2019.

Investment priorities have evolved over the years. In the 1990s particular importance was attached to the provision of telecommunications infrastructure and development of gas network. Then there was the period of water supply and sewage investments. For some time, transport investments, including road and purchase of rolling stock have been high in the hierarchy of needs. However for over a decade, more and more local governments have been focusing on cultural, sporting and recreational activities.⁷⁵

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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Galiński P, 'Determinants of Debt Limits in Local Governments: Case of Poland' (2013) 213 *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 376

⁷⁴ The operating surplus is the positive difference between current revenue and current expenditure. Accordingly, the negative result between current revenue and current expenditure represents an operating deficit.

⁷⁵ Swianiewicz Paweł and Łukomska Julita, 'Liderzy inwestycji. Ranking wydatków inwestycyjnych samorządów 2015-2017' (*Wspólnota*, 20 January 2020) <https://www.wspolnota.org.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/Andrzej/11_2017/Nr_19_Ranking_-_Wydatki_inwestycyjne_2015-2017.pdf> accessed 2 November 2019.

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